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Research Article

Assessment Of Knowledge, Attitude, And Practice On Breast Cancer And Breast Self-Examination Among Female Population: An Online Survey

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ABSTRACT

Breast cancer is the second most common cancer among women globally, with a high mortality rate. This study assessed knowledge, attitude, and practice regarding breast cancer and breast self-examination (BSE) through an online survey of 102 women. Most participants were aged 20-30 years (68.6%) and 61.8% were single, primarily students (46%). The main source of information was the internet (57.8%) about breast cancer. The survey revealed that most participants had good knowledge and a positive attitude towards breast cancer and BSE. However, 53.9% did not practice BSE. The main reasons for not practicing BSE were the absence of breast problems (45%) and a lack of knowledge on how to perform BSE (31%). Among those who practiced BSE, 35% inspected their breasts in a mirror, 35.6% practiced monthly, 2.2% performed BSE within 2-3 days after menstruation, and 40% did it whenever it came to mind. The study finds that while respondents are aware of breast cancer and BSE, their knowledge of proper BSE practices is lacking. Increased awareness programs and integrating BSE education into high school curricula are recommended to enhance sexual and reproductive health education.

INTRODUCTION

Cancer is a disease in which the cells divide uncontrollably affecting the body tissues and organs. There are more than 100 different types of cancer worldwide. The different types of cancer are named for its affecting on the particular part,

organ or tissues.[1] Breast cancer, the second most common cancer in women globally, arises from uncontrolled cell division in the breast, leading to lumps. It can be invasive or non-invasive. Early diagnosis can make it curable, while late diagnosis can be life-threatening.[2] Advancing age, early

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menarche, late menopause, late pregnancy, genetic factors and having dense breasts are some of the risk factors along with gender.[3] Breast cancer can be self-screened using Breast Self-Examination (BSE), which is crucial for early diagnosis. BSE involves inspecting and feeling one's own breasts for any changes.[4]

OBJECTIVES

- To assess the knowledge on Breast cancer
- To assess the knowledge attitude and practice of Breast Self-Examination.

METHODOLOGY

Study site:

The study was an online survey which was conducted among the community.

Study design and sampling:

This cross-sectional observational study used an online survey with structured questionnaires to assess knowledge, attitude, and practice regarding breast cancer and breast self-examination (BSE). The questionnaire, created and disseminated via Google Forms, was shared through social media platforms. Participants were encouraged to complete the survey and share it with their family and friends. To ensure data integrity, each participant was limited to one response. The study enrolled people during the time schedule (1/02/2023 to 30/03/2023) allotted for the project including other circumstances. Inclusion criteria: The female populations aged between 20 to 70 years who were willing to participate and voluntarily enrolled.

Exclusion criteria:

males and Female population aged below 20 years and above 70 years

METHOD OF COLLECTION OF DATA:

Data Collection Procedure:

Data was collected through an online survey using a structured questionnaire designed to assess women's knowledge, attitude, and practice regarding breast cancer and breast self-examination (BSE). The questionnaire, prepared in English, was based on articles from online sources such as PubMed and Google Scholar, and adapted from previous studies to suit the objectives of this study.

Data Processing And Analysis:

Sample characteristics were computed in percentage/suitable and it is presented using tables and figures.

RESULT

The present study was aimed to assess knowledge, attitude and practice on Breast Cancer and Breast Self-Examination among female population. A total of 102 participants participated in the online based survey.

Scio-Demographic details:

The socio-demographic details (Table 1) show that 68.6% of participants were aged 20-30 years, with 12.7%, 5.9%, 6.9%, and 5.9% in the age ranges of 31-40, 41-50, 51-60, and 61-70 years, respectively. Most participants were single (61.8%), reflecting the majority age group of 20-30 years, while 33.3% were married, and 4.9% were widowed. Among the 102 participants, 46% were students, 22% were in academics/teaching, 11% were homemakers, 9% were healthcare workers, 9% were in the private sector, and 3% were retired. All participants had heard about breast cancer, with 78.4% reporting no family history and 21.6% reporting a family history of breast cancer (see Fig. 1).

Table no. 1: Socio-Demographic details of participants (N=102)

Characteristics	Frequency	Percentage
Age in years		
• 20-30yrs		
• 31-40yrs	70	68.6%
• 41-50yrs	13	12.7%,
• 51-60yrs	6	5.9%,

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 61-70yrs 	7 6	6.9%, 5.9%
Marital Status <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Single • Married • Widowed 	63 34 5	61.8% 33.3% 4.9%
Occupation <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Home maker • Academic/teaching <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Student • Private sector • Healthcare worker • Others (Retired) 	11 23 47 9 9 3	10.8% 22.5% 46.1% 8.8% 8.8% 3%
Have you heard about Breast Cancer? Yes	102	100%
History of Breast Cancer in family <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Present • Absent 	22 80	22.6% 78.4%

Sources of information about Breast Cancer: (57.8%) and least being others (education) (15%)
 The major source of information about the Breast Cancer to the participants was from Internet and social campaign (20.6%). (Fig no. 1)

Fig no. 1: Sources of information about Breast Cancer

Knowledge on Breast Cancer:

Knowledge plays a crucial role in breast cancer and breast self-examination (BSE). Table 2 indicates that participants were highly aware of breast cancer. To assess their knowledge of risk factors and signs of breast cancer, participants were asked to select multiple options based on

their knowledge. The perceived risk factors, in order of prevalence among respondents, were positive family history (70.6%), exposure to radiation (58.8%), hormone replacement therapy (49%), smoking (45.1%), oral contraceptives (44.1%), late menopause (39.2%), obesity (35.3%), non-lactating women (33.3%), early

menarche (29.4%), lack of physical exercise (29.4%), old age (25.5%), unmarried or without children (24.5%), consumption of fatty food (24.5%), and 23.5% did not know. The most commonly recognized signs of breast cancer included a lump in the breast (76.5%), pain in the

breast or nipples (63.7%), lump or thickening under the armpit (62.7%), discharge from the breast nipples (54.9%), change in size of the breast or nipples (52.9%), inverted nipples (42.2%), puckering or dimpling of the breast nipple (39.2%), and 13.7% of respondents did not know.

Table no. 2: Knowledge regarding Breast cancer and Breast Self-examination (BSE)

Knowledge	Frequency	Percentage
Risk factors of Breast cancer		
• Positive family history	72	70.6%
• Late menopause	40	39.2%
• Unmarried or without children	25	24.5%
• Non-lactating women (during lifetime)	34	33.3%
• Old age	26	25.5%
• Early menarche	30	29.4%
• Consumption of fatty food	25	24.5%
• Hormone replacement therapy	50	49%
• Oral contraceptives	45	44.1%
• Lack of physical exercise	30	29.4%
• Obesity	36	35.3%
• Smoking	46	45.1%
• Exposure to radiation	60	58.8%
• Don't know	24	23.5%
Signs of Breast cancer		
• Inverted nipples	43	42.2%
• Dissimilarity or change in size of breast or nipples	54	52.9%
• Puckering or dimpling of breast size	40	39.2%
• Pain in the breast or nipple	65	63.7%
• Lump or thickening under armpit	64	62.7%
• Discharge from the breast nipple	56	54.9%
• Lump in the breast	78	76.5%
• Don't know	14	13.7%
Best method for early diagnosis of Breast Cancer		
• By using Fine needle Aspiration Cytology (FNAC)	2	2%
• Mammography	15	14.7%
• Breast self-examination	57	55.9%
• Ultrasound	2	2%
	25	24.5%
	1	1%

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • By doctor • Don't know 		
Age at which BSE should Be started <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • From birth • From 30yrs • From puberty • After menopause • From 20yrs • Not sure 	0 27 24 8 41 2	0% 26.5% 23.5% 7.8% 40.2% 2%
Do you think Breast cancer can be cured if detected early? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes • No • Don't know 	90 4 8	88.2% 3.9% 7.8%

Knowledge on Breast self-examination:

Breast self-examination (BSE) is one of the self methods to diagnose Breast cancer at early stage. More than 50% of the respondents responded that Breast Self-Examination (55.9%) is the best method for early diagnosis of Breast Cancer and followed by using Fine Needle Aspiration Cytology (FNAC) 2%, mammography 14.7%, ultrasound 2%, by doctor 24.5%, 1% Didn't know. Majority of the participants 40.2% responded that Breast Self-Examination should be started from the age 20years and 2% were not sure when to start BSE. 88.2% of them think that Breast cancer can be cured if detected early, 3.9% think it can't be cured and 7.8% don't know. (Table no.2)

Attitude towards Breast Cancer:

The attitude of a person towards any disease is important so as to integrate the meaningfulness, comprehensibility and manageability of a situation or disease. The (Table no. 3) shows, the attitude of participants towards Breast Cancer and Breast Self-Examination. 45.1% agreed that Breast Cancer is preventable, 21.6% disagreed and 33.3% neither agree nor disagree. 92.2% agreed that early diagnosis of Breast cancer increases the chance of recovery, 2% disagreed, 5.9% neither agree nor disagree. 37.3 % agreed that improving personal hygiene can reduce risk of developing Breast Cancer, 31.4% disagreed, 31.4% neither agree nor disagree. (Fig no. 3)

Fig no. 2: Attitude towards Breast cancer

Attitude towards Breast self-examination:

91.2% responded that females above 20yrs of age should practice BSE frequently, 80.4%

participants response was practicing BSE should be made mandatory and 97% responded that females must be educated about BSE. (Fig no. 4)

Fig no. 3: Attitude towards Breast Self-Examination (BSE)

Practice of Breast self-examination:

Practicing BSE is crucial for early tumor detection, as women are more likely to discover tumors themselves with regular practice. Among 102 participants, 53.9% did not practice BSE, while 46.1% did. Reasons for not practicing included unawareness (15%), lack of breast problems

(45%), not knowing how (31%), and belief that it's unnecessary (9%). Of those who practiced BSE, 35% used a mirror, 26% felt the breast with their hand, 14% felt the armpit, 16% performed it during a shower, and 9% while lying down. Only 35.6% practiced monthly, 2.2% within 2-3 days after menstruation, and 40% did it irregularly.

Table no. 3: Practice of Breast Self-Examination

Practice	Frequency	Percentage
Do you practice BSE		
• Yes	47	46.1%
• No	55	53.9%
If no, what is the reason		
• Unaware of the need	8	15%
• Don't have breast problems	25	45%
• Don't know how to do BSE	17	31%
• Don't think I should	5	9%
How do you perform BSE		
• Inspecting the breast in mirror	19	35%
• Feeling the breast with hand	33	26%
• Feeling the armpit with hand	17	14%
• During shower	20	16%
• On the bed lying down	11	9%
How often do you perform BSE		
• Monthly	16	35.6%
• Every 6months	3	6.7%
• Annually	5	11.1%
• When it comes to my mind	18	40%
• Within 2-3 days after session of menstruation	1	2.2%
• Few days before menstruation starts	2	4.4%

DISCUSSION

Breast cancer is a leading cause of death in women due to late diagnosis, often due to inadequate knowledge and practice of risk factors, signs, and BSE. This study found that participants had good knowledge of breast cancer signs and BSE, though this finding may not align with Okabia et al. (5) and Yerpude et al (6) In our present study most of the participants were in the age group of 20-

30years (68.6%). Age is also related to the extent of awareness which is similar to the study conducted by Yerpude et al. (6) Among 102 participants, majority had known about the symptoms of Breast Cancer which is unsupported by Khadilkar et al.(7) Very less respondents have positive family history of Breast Cancer than the study done by Azubuike et al. (8) The present study suggests that most of the participants had

good attitude towards Breast Cancer and Breast self-examination that early diagnosis of Breast Cancer increases the chance of recovery Which is supported by Ahmed N et al. (9), and they were aware that it is preventable which is supported by Hoseini ZS et al. (10) In the present study majority of participants had a positive attitude towards Breast self-examination, which is comparable with the study done by Abhay M et al. (4) In the current study majority of participants were aware of various BSE practices which is similar to the study conducted by Allohaib A et al. (11) But only 46.1% practice BSE and only 6.7% of the participants performed it every 6months, 35.6% responded that they perform BSE monthly while 40% of them performed it whenever they felt like doing it which is similar to the results of study conducted by Joyce C et al. (12) 53.9% don't practice thinking they don't have Breast problems as in the study comparing to Dahiya M et al. (13)

FUTURE PROSPECTIVES

Our findings highlight the need for further research to accurately assess the knowledge, attitude, and practice of breast cancer and BSE among females, especially older women, and across culturally diverse and urban-rural settings.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion most respondents were aware of breast cancer and BSE, their knowledge of proper BSE practices was inadequate. This highlights the need for more awareness programs and the inclusion of BSE education in high school curricula. Effective educational programs on BSE are crucial for improving early detection and reducing breast cancer morbidity and mortality.

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